

The Indian-French TRISHNA mission will monitor coastal waters from space

Philippe GAMET (CNES/CESBIO, Philippe.Gamet@cnes.fr, ORCID 0000-0002-3153-9573), Emmanuelle AUTRET (IFREMER), Sébastien MARCQ (CNES)
 Anne LIFERMANN (CNES), Jean-Louis ROUJEAN (CNRS/CESBIO), Bimal K. BHATTACHARYA (ISRO/SAC), Philippe MAISONGRANDE (CNES), K. R. MANJUNATH (ISRO/URSC), Corinne SALCEDO (CNES), Dheeraj ADLAKHA (ISRO/SAC),
 Laurence BUFFET (CNES), Thierry CARLIER (CNES), Emilie DELOGU (CNES), Renaud BINET (CNES), Mark IRVINE (INRAE), Gilles BOULET (IRD/CESBIO), Xavier BRIOTTET (ONERA), Ghislain PICARD (IGE), Pascal ALLEMAND (LGL)

TRISHNA for Water management

~+2 billions people by 2050

- Pressure \uparrow on energy and food
- Pressure \uparrow on transboundary basins
- Population \uparrow in fluvial & coastal zones

Biodiversity / pressure on the habitats

- In Rivers, wetlands, coastal zones
- Modified by dams (connectivity), pollution (health)

Global warming +2deg by 2050

- Impact on Carbon and water cycles
- Extrem events: droughts, floods, storms, fires

GOGLAM
Global Agricultural Monitoring

Essential Agricultural Variables
→ meet current and evolving policy drivers for agriculture

- Adaptation, mitigation Stakes
- Involving Science and Application levels in economy, ecology, geopolitics, security...
- Reliable metrics needed, homogeneous along time and on every scale from global to regional

TRISHNA mission for oceans at a glance

- Indian-French satellite mission, launch in 2025, 5-year lifetime
- Global coverage of all coastal areas (+100km from the coastline)
- VNIR water reflectances + SST in the same Level-2 product
- High-resolution (60m), high revisit (< 3 days), high precision & accuracy (1K Sea Surface Temperature)
- Day & Night acquisitions with overpass time = 1 PM & 1 AM at Equator
- Free and open data policy for scientific community

Continental surfaces, coastal areas (100km) and closed seas

TRISHNA average revisit is less than 3 days

Mission datasheet

Band name	Wavelength Center (nm)	FWHM (nm)
Blue	485	70
Green	555	70
Red	670	60
NIR	860	40
WV	910	30
Cirrus	1380	30
SWIR	1610	100

TIR 1	8.65	0.35
TIR 2	9.0	0.35
TIR 3	10.6	0.7
TIR 4	11.6	1.0

Spectral Bands

- ☐ ISRO/CNES cooperation, launch 2025, 5-year lifetime
- ☐ Scientific & operational applications
- ☐ Focus on **ecosystem stress and water use + coastal & inland waters**
- ☐ Global coverage of continental and coastal areas
- ☐ 60 meters nadir spatial resolution (VIS-NIR-SWIR-TIR)
- ☐ 4 LWIR bands + 5 VNIR bands + 2 SWIR bands
- ☐ Revisit : 3 acquisitions at equator per 8 days period
- ☐ 761km-8day orbit reducing hot spot constraints in intertropical zone
- ☐ ± 34° scan angle, 1030km swath
- ☐ Overpass time : 1 PM (LTDN)
- ☐ NeDT 0.2K
- ☐ Indo-French(*) Joint Science Team (*) with other contributors
- ☐ Synergies with ECOSTRESS, SBG, LSTM science & application teams
- ☐ Free and open data policy for worldwide scientific community
- ☐ Level-2 products include reflectance, LST, LSE, EvapoTranspiration & Stress Index
- ☐ Secondary objectives: urban, cryosphere, Solid Earth, Atmosphere

TRISHNA Products

All products also include quality flags

Level	Products
Level 1C	TOA reflectance (x7 VNIR/SWIR bands), TOA radiance (x4 LWIR bands), Cloud mask <i>Radiometrically and geometrically calibrated - Orthorectified and resampled on a uniform spatial grid (Sentinel-2 tiles, Copernicus DEM)</i>
Level 2A	Land Surface Temperature / Sea Surface Temperature, Surface reflectance, Total Water Vapor Content Land Surface Emissivity (x4 LWIR bands), Cloud mask, Aerosol Optical Thickness
Level 2B	Surface albedo, Green Area Index, fAPAR, Fraction of Vegetation Cover <i>Energy balance at time of acquisition</i> , <i>Daily ecosystem stress variables</i> EvapoTranspiration & Stress Index, Daily EvapoTranspiration and daily stress
Level 3	Temporal and/or spatial synthesis of level 2 variables, <i>Daily ecosystem stress variables with gap-filling</i> Daily EvapoTranspiration and daily stress

Coastal and Inland Waters

Area	What is at stake	What TRISHNA brings
Coastal Waters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mixing processes • Water Quality, algal bloom, halieutic resource, spring discharge (resurgence), discharge of water, pollutants • Ecosystem Productivity (phytoplankton) • Halieutic resource • Melting and frost Processes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> TEMPERATURE REFLECTANCES COLOR INDICES
Inland waters		
Sea Ice		

Cryosphere

Area	What is at stake	What TRISHNA brings
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sea ice, Ice sheets, Ice caps Snow & Glaciers Permafrost, Seasonally frozen ground River & lake ice 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Snow-melt runoff and debris thickness estimation • Snow cover change & metamorphism at sub-watershed scale • Modelling snow energy fluxes • Snow mass, Snow Water Equivalent (SWE), Snow depth 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> TEMPERATURE (Day & Night) EMISSIVITY Snow and Ice Albedo Snow cover